

ReCiPSS

D8.1-Project website

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Draft

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1. Executive Summary

This document addresses the result of the Task 8.1: Developing the project website and intranet that focused on the development of an external project website hosted at <http://www.recipss.eu/>. It also contains a description of Planview Projectplace®¹ (www.projectplace.com), the project management platform used as the internal repository as well as for internal communication and collaboration.

The website includes a summary of the project, presentation of the consortium, large scale demonstrators description, related initiatives, project news and events. It also contains a list of public deliverables from the project, together with publications, white papers and reports.

A partner-restricted information repository will be hosted for regular (non-classified) project internal communication and collaboration.

This document seeks to describe the structure and the main functionalities – pages, sub-pages, sliders, graphic, current content, menu, etc. – included in the project website.

In order to complete this task, the task leader (SIVECO):

- Created the website map and validated with all partners.
- Created/collected the website content and validated with all partners.
- Implemented and released the website.

¹ Planview Projectplace® platform is a commercial service provided for ReCiPSS under an agreement between KTH and SUNET. The platform features more functionalities than what have been described in section 3. Further queries about the platform should be referred to Planview Projectplace®.

2. Website start-up

The address of the **ReCiPSS** website is: <http://www.recipss.eu/>

The structure of the **ReCiPSS** website is as follows:

- ✓ Home
 - Summary of the project
 - Project News
 - Events
- ✓ About us
 - Consortium
 - Advisory Board
- ✓ The Project
 - Objectives
 - Large-Scale Demonstrators
 - Impact
 - Related Initiatives
- ✓ Results
 - Deliverables
 - Reports
 - White papers
 - Publications
- ✓ Press and Media
 - News
 - Press Releases
 - Newsletter
 - Media
 - Promotional Materials
 - Presentations
- ✓ Contact us

Figure 1 : ReCiPSS website structure and pages header

All the sections/pages presented above can be accessed through the Main menu, visible in all pages of the website.

2.1. Home

The Home page aims to provide a Summary of the Project, including Project News and Events related to ReCiPSS project.

The first page will appear as in the image below:

Figure 2 : ReCiPSS website home page

The **Home** page includes also a slider zone with pictures relevant for the project’s topic. If the left arrow button or the right arrow button is pressed, the visitor can see the homepage slides.

Figure 3 : ReCiPSS slider buttons

The slides that will be displayed are captured in the following pictures.

Figure 4 : ReCiPSS first slide

Figure 5 : ReCiPSS second slide

2.1.1. Summary of the project

In the **Summary of the project** section a short presentation of the project is displayed.

Summary of the project

As part of the European Research Framework H2020, the European Commission supports the European industry in the large-scale build-up and implementation of circular manufacturing systems in order to drive a development towards a stable circular economy in the EU. The Research Project "Resource-Efficient Circular Product-Service-Systems" (ReCiPSS), kicked off on June 1st 2018.

[Read More](#)

Figure 6 : Home page Summary of the project section

The entire content is shown in **Summary of the project** page which can be accessed either through **Read More** button or through **Summary of the project** menu element.

Figure 7 : Summary of the project menu element

2.1.2. Project News

The **Project News** section displays the summary of the last three articles published in any of the **News**, **Press Releases** and **Newsletter** sections from **Press and Media Menu**.

Figure 8 : Home page Project News section

In order to access the full page which contains a complete list for news, the visitor must click the **Project News** menu element.

Figure 9 : Project News menu element

Figure 10 : Project News section

For each news from **Project News** a Linked in pictogram is displayed that allows visitors to share the content on his/her Linked In account by clicking the pictogram.

Figure 11 : Project News dedicated page

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between news.

2.1.3. Events

In the **Events** section the last two articles from the Events page are displayed. Also, a calendar with events is shown.

Events

World Remanufacturing Confer...

September 19, 2018

The ReCiPSS projects will be presented at an important event, World Remanufacturing Conference, during September 2018 thanks to FRAUNHOFER team. You can find more details for this event here: <https://www.worldremanconference.com/>

Read more

ReCiPSS R&D team meets with ...

August 29, 2018

Part of the ReCiPSS R&D team from TU Delft, CirBES and Masaryk University gathered in Velenje to meet Gorenje. The goal of the visit has been to understand the current state (the starting point) of the white good demonstrator. The team met several people from operations to management working in supply chain, design, marketing, finance, [...]

Read more

Calendar

<< Sep 2018 >>

M	T	W	T	F	S	S
27	28	29	30	31	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

Figure 12 : Home page Events section

Visitor can see the complete events list accessing the **Events** menu element. (Home -> Events)

HOME | ABOUT US | THE PROJECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US

Summary of the project

Project News

Events

Events

Figure 13 : Events menu element

HOME | ABOUT US | THE PROJECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US

Events

World Remanufacturing Confer...

September 13, 2018

The ReCiPSS projects will be presented at an important event, World Remanufacturing Conference, during September 2018 thanks to FRAUNHOFER team. You can find more details for this event here: <https://www.worldremanconference.com/>

Read more

Figure 14 : Events section

Figure 15 : Events dedicated page

For each event from **Events** section a Linked in pictogram is displayed that allows visitors to share the content on his/her Linked In account by clicking the pictogram.

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between events from **Events**.

2.1.4. Consortium

A slider with the logos of the project partners is displayed.

Figure 16 : Home page Consortium section

The slider moves automatically in order that all the 13 consortium partners to be displayed.

2.1.5. Footer section

This section is shown on every page of the website. It contains the project logo, the project LinkedIn Social Media page link and the Privacy Policy statement (Detailed in Annex A). Also, in the bottom of this section, an EU disclaimer is shown.

Figure 17 : Footer section

2.2. About Us

2.2.1. Consortium

This page is accessible from the **About Us** menu element.

HOME | ABOUT US | THE PROJECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US

Figure 18 : Consortium menu element

This menu element displays a page with all the partners' descriptions and logos.

Figure 19 : Consortium page

By clicking **View partner's site button** the visitor will be directed to the partner's website.

2.2.2. Advisory Board

Advisory Board is the second page which can be accessed under **About Us** menu.

Figure 20 : Advisory Board menu element

2.3. The project

2.3.1. Objectives

This page displays the objectives of the project. It can be accessible under **The Project** menu.

Figure 21 : Objectives menu element

2.3.2. Large-Scale Demonstrators

This page displays a short description for the two Large scale demonstrators: Gorenje demonstrator (white goods demonstrator) and Bosch Demonstrator (Automotive spare demonstrator).

Figure 22 : Large-Scale Demonstrators menu element

2.3.3. Impact

This page summaries the estimated Impact expected by implementation of the ReCiPSS project.

Figure 23 : Impact menu element

2.3.4. Related initiatives

This page lists all the related initiatives for ReCiPSS project. This could include active H2020 projects, previous initiatives on circular economy, past projects with similar topic implemented/under implementation by partners.

Figure 24 : Related Initiatives menu element

Figure 25 : Related Initiatives page

2.4. Results

2.4.1. Deliverables

This page lists all the public deliverables from ReCiPSS project. Once a deliverable is completed will be uploaded on the website and can be downloaded by visitors by clicking Download button.

The screenshot shows the ReCiPSS website header with navigation links: HOME | ABOUT US | THE PROJECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US. A dropdown menu is open under 'RESULTS', showing 'Deliverables', 'Reports', 'White papers', and 'Publications'. Below the menu is a table of deliverables:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead benefici		
D2.1	Demonstrator baseline and market characteristics report	MU	12	Download
D2.3	Circular business models evaluation reports	MU	36	Download
D3.1	Baseline and target design report	TUD	8	Download
D3.4	Circular design methodologies development status report	TUD	39	Download

Figure 26 : Deliverables menu element and page

2.4.2. Reports

This page lists all the public reports produced by ReCiPSS project partners.

The screenshot shows the ReCiPSS website header with navigation links: HOME | ABOUT US | THE PROJECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US. A dropdown menu is open under 'RESULTS', showing 'Deliverables', 'Reports', and 'White papers'. The 'Reports' menu item is highlighted, and the 'Reports' page content is visible in the background.

Figure 27 : Reports menu element

By clicking read more the visitor is directed to the **Reports** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to share the content on his/her Linked In account and

also could press on pdf button in order to download the **Reports** in .pdf format.

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between **Reports**.

2.4.3. White Papers

This page lists all the white papers produced by ReCiPSS project’s partners.

Figure 28 : White papers menu element

By clicking read more the visitor is directed to the **White papers** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the **White papers** in .pdf format. The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between white papers.

2.4.4. Publications

This page lists all the publications produced by ReCiPSS project’s partners.

Figure 29 : Publication menu element

By clicking read more the visitor is directed to the **Publication** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the **Publication** in .pdf format. The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between publications.

2.5. Press and Media

2.5.1. News

On this page are presented **News** about the project. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the News section from **Press and Media** Menu.

Figure 30 : News menu element

Figure 31 : News page section

By clicking **Read more** button the visitor is directed to the **News** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to share the content on his/her Linked In account.

Figure 32 : News dedicated page

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between news.

2.5.2. Press Releases

On this page are presented Press Releases about the project. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the Press Releases section from **Press and Media** Menu.

Figure 33 : Press releases menu element

Figure 34 : Press releases section

By clicking read more the visitor is directed to the Press Release dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the press release in .pdf format.

01 Aug 2018 A H2020 research and innovation project

The European Commission supports industry in large scale implementation of Circular Manufacturing Systems – a drive towards a stable circular economy.

Resource-efficient Circular Product-Service Systems (ReCiPSS) is a research project kicked-off on June, 1st 2018.

Two industrial large-scale demonstrators of the Automotive and the White Goods industry are involved in the project. ReCiPSS is co-funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776577-2.

As part of the white goods demonstrator, Gorenje gospodinjiski aparati d. d., one of the leading European household appliances producer, will implement an innovative circular pay-per-wash scheme for washing machines in 4 European countries.

As part of the automotive spare parts demonstrator, the Circular Economy Solutions GmbH together with Robert Bosch GmbH will streamline the reverse logistics flow for 80,000 cores, enabling aftermarket stakeholders to close the loop by using a single service provider for reverse logistics and by simplifying the existing complex trade levels.

The CoremanNet service network, well established in the European automotive aftermarket, will be the first to integrate these new services in its infrastructure.

To successfully implement the demonstrators, ReCiPSS will develop further circular tools/methodologies and will develop ICT platforms allowing data exchange for both cases. The platforms and the data exchange will enable usage tracking and remote monitoring, in the case of washing machines and value chain collaboration, in the case of automotive parts.

The project brings together 13 partners from 8 countries and will be coordinated by the KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden, with the support of a unique consortium of experts, which consist of 4 research and 9 industrial partners.

More information about the project will be available soon at www.recipss.eu (the website is under construction).

Figure 35 : Press releases dedicated page

Figure 36 : Example of pdf format of the Press Release

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between Press Releases.

2.5.3. Newsletter

On this page are presented project’s **Newsletters**. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the **Newsletters** section from **Press and Media** Menu.

Figure 37 : Newsletter menu element

By clicking read more the visitor is directed to the **Newsletters** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the **Newsletters** in .pdf format. The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between Newsletters.

2.5.4. Media

On this page are presented project’s **Media** files. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the **Media** section from **Press and Media** Menu.

Figure 38 : Media menu element

By clicking **View** the visitor is directed to the **Media** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to share the content on his/her Linked In account . The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between **Media** files.

2.5.5. Promotional materials

On this page are presented project's **Promotional Materials** files. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the **Promotional Materials** section from **Press and Media** Menu.

Figure 39 : Promotional materials menu element and page

By clicking **View** the visitor is directed to the **Promotional Materials** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the promotional material in .pdf format.

12 Sep 2014 Recipss flyer 2

Figure 40 : Promotional material example

The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between **Promotional Materials**.

2.5.6. Presentations

On this page are presented project's **Presentations** files. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the **Presentations** section from **Press and Media** Menu.

ECT | RESULTS | PRESS AND MEDIA | CONTACT US

Figure 41 : Presentations menu element

By clicking **View** the visitor is directed to the **Presentations** dedicated page. From this page the visitor can click on *Linked In* pictogram in order to download the **Presentations** in .pdf format. The buttons **Previous** and **Next** allow the visitors to navigate between **Presentations**.

2.6. Contact Us

On this page information about contact details for this project are displayed in order that visitors are able to contact the project coordinator. The information can be consulted by the visitor by accessing the **Contact Us** Menu.

Figure 42 : Contact us page

3. Internal information repository: Planview Projectplace®

Planview Projectplace®, a project management software from Planview², is used for the ReCiPSS internal communication and collaboration. The structure of the ReCiPSS workspace in Planview Projectplace® is as follows:

- Overview
- Conversations
- Plan
- Board
- Documents
- Meetings
- Issues
- Members
- Recycle Bin

Figure 43 : Planview Projectplace® structure and pages header

3.1. Overview

The **Overview** section aims to provide an overview of the current status of the ReCiPSS project as shown in Figure 44.

² Planview is a global enterprise software company headquartered in Austin, Texas

Figure 44 : Overview section

The **Milestone** window provides an overview of the upcoming milestones including a short description and the deadline as shown in Figure 45.

Figure 45 : Milestones section

The **Cards and Activities** dashboard gives visibility into ongoing work as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46: Cards and Activities dashboard

The **Recent document** section shows the documents that are recently uploaded or modified. For each document it is reported the author who modified it, the type of change and the date of change as shown in Figure 47. By clicking on the individual document, a separate window opens that shows a detailed information about the document and actions that can be performed (e.g. open, share, comments, etc.).

Recent documents		Ongoing activities	Scheduled work
Name	Modified By	Last change	Date ↑
press_release_template.doc	Adriana Prodan	Commented	Today 11:59
20180910_Feedback Homepage.docx	Adriana Prodan	Copied	Today 11:56
ReCiPSS-D8.1 Project Website-FINAL.doc	Adriana Prodan	Commented	Today 11:52
ReCiPSS-D8.1 Project Website v1.doc	Adriana Prodan	Commented	Today 11:03

Figure 47 : Recent documents section

The **Ongoing activities** section shows a list of the current activities and their due date as shown in Figure 48. By clicking on the individual activity a separate window opens, that shows a detailed information about the activity and the actions that can be performed.

Recent documents		Ongoing activities	Scheduled work	All
Name	Board	Cards	Due date ↑	
45) D10.3 : GEN - Requirement No. 3 [KTH]	No board	0/0	28 days overdue	
29) D8.1 : Project website [SIV]	No board	0/0	Due in 2 days	
43) D10.1 : H - Requirement No. 1 [KTH]	No board	0/0	Due in 63 days	

Figure 48 : Ongoing activities section

The **Recent conversations** sections reports the latest conversations between the members of the project as shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49 : Recent conversations sections

3.2. Conversations

The **Conversations** tool shown in Figure 50 is used for communicating within the members of the project.

Figure 50 : Conversations tool

3.3. Plan

The **Plan** tool visualizes the work using a traditional work breakdown structure on the left and a Gantt chart on the right as shown in Figure 51. In the *Plan* tool it is possible to add activities, milestones and important dates to the plan. The work that is being done on each activity can be seen by cards connected to the activity.

Figure 51 : Plan tool

3.4. Documents

The **Documents** tool serves as a file repository and is used to share files and collaborate. The files can be organized into folders as shown in Figure 52.

Figure 52 : Documents tool

A document can be opened, shared or sent for review as shown in Figure 53. All the comments regarding the document are also visualized.

Figure 53: Individual file view

3.5. Meetings

The **Meetings** tool is used for managing meetings as shown in Figure 54.

Figure 54 : Meetings tool

3.6. Members

In the **Members** tool a list of all the members participating in the project is reported including their contact information as shown in Figure 55.

Name	Type	Email	Description	Organisation	Last logged in
Adriana Prodan Project Manager	Member	adriana.prodan@siveco.ro		SIVECO Romania	28 Sep
Alena Klápalová PIU	Member	alena.klapalova@econ.muni.cz			26 Sep
Ales Mihalic Dr.	Member	ales.mihalic@gorenje.com		Gorenje d.d.	10 Sep
All members	Group		Automatically generated group with all project members.		
Amir Rashid Asst. Prof.	Member	amir@kth.se		Kungliga Tekniska högskolan	6 Jul
Andreas Schroeder	Member	andreas.schroeder@de.bosch.com			24 Sep
Birgit Kresenzl	Member	birgit.kresenzl@de.bosch.com			21 Aug
Christoph Vette	Member	christoph.vette@ipa.fraunhofer.de		Fraunhofer IPA	28 Sep
Claudia Thönnessen	Member	claudia.thoennessen@c-eco.com			28 Sep
Claudiu Burtea	Member	claudiu.burtea@siveco.ro			24 Sep
Colin Bom CEO	Member	colin.bom@homegroup.com		Home B.V.	28 Sep
Conny Bakker Professor	Member	C.A.Bakker@tudelft.nl	Conny Bakker	TU Delft	25 Sep
Daniela Boari	Member	daniela.boari@siveco.ro			16 Jul
Daniela Buleandra	Member	daniela.buleandra@siveco.ro			18 Jul
DAVID POC Research Director/Project Mana	Member	david.poc@econ.muni.cz		Masaryk University, Faculty of Ec	5 Sep
Dominik Kuntz Operations Project Manager	Member	dominik.kuntz@c-eco.com		Circular Economy Solutions Gmt	13 Sep
Farazee Muhammed Abdul Researcher	Head administrator	ess@kth.se		KTH Royal Institute of Technolog	25 Sep
Jan van Mierlo	Member	jan.vanmierlo@c-eco.com		Circular Economy Solutions Gmt	25 Sep
Jan van Os	Member	janos@atagbenelux.com		ATAG Benelux	28 Sep
Jean-michel Strasser					

Figure 55 : Members tool

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4. Conclusions

The current deliverable presents the dissemination project website and the partner-restricted information repository used for internal communication and collaboration. Considering the project's duration (4 years) the website could evolve and new features could be implemented in order to cover project's needs related to dissemination objectives. The documentation will be updated each time a new feature will be added to this website. The content of the dissemination website will be permanently updated.

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5. Annex A- Privacy Policy

Standard Disclaimer

We will link to external sites that help us perform our mission – to inform about the ReCiPSS project. Links to external sites do not imply any official ReCiPSS endorsement of the opinions or ideas expressed therein, or guarantee the validity of the information provided. Links will be provided to external sites that are managed in a professional manner (i.e., it is fully operational, is available most of the time, does not serve inaccurate information or obscene graphics, etc.). This server will not link to external servers if such a link would appear to provide an official endorsement of fundraising efforts or lobbying for a political agenda. Images of individuals are the personal property of the person displayed.

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Privacy

This website uses Google Analytics, a web analytics service provided by Google, Inc. ("Google"). Google Analytics uses "cookies", which are text files placed on your computer, to help the website analyze how visitor use the site. The information generated by the cookie about your use of the website will be transmitted to and stored by Google on servers in the United States. In case IP-anonymisation is activated on this website, your IP address will be truncated within the area of Member States of the European Union or other parties to the Agreement on the European Economic Area. Only in exceptional cases the whole IP address will be first transferred to a Google server in the USA and truncated there. The IP-anonymisation is active on this website. Google will use this information on behalf of the operator of this website for the purpose of evaluating your use of the website, compiling reports on website activity for website operators and providing them other services relating to website activity and internet usage. The IP-address, that your Browser conveys within the scope of Google Analytics, will not be associated with any other data held by Google. You may refuse the use of cookies by selecting the appropriate settings on your browser, however please note that if you do this you may not be able to use the full functionality of this website. You can also opt-out from being tracked by Google Analytics with effect for the future by downloading and installing Google Analytics Opt-out Browser Addon for your current web browser: tools.google.com/dlpage/gaoptout.

All pictures uploaded on the website are based on a verbal permission to take the photos. Anyone not wishing to appear on a group photograph will then have the opportunity to opt out.

All the images uploaded to the website will not have embedded location data (EXIF GPS) included. Visitors to the website can download and extract any location data from images on the website.

Copyright Statement

Please note: You are welcome to make a link to any of the web pages the Service has published on the internet. There is no need to request permission. Not all the information on our site is in the public domain. Some images/graphics are licensed for use under the copyright law, and the use of the Service logo is restricted to official publications. Before using any images and graphics please contact us in order to receive our confirmation (info@recipss.eu). We will identify material we use from sources outside the Service, and request others do the same when using information published by the Service.

Webmaster

Comments to this website are most welcome. Please send us an email to info@recipss.eu.